

Jainism

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Jain Traditions, Digambara, Svetambara, Murtipujak, Non-Murtipujak, Nonsectarian

Scholarship on Jain religious traditions of South Asia and the diaspora

Date Range: 600 BCE - 2020 CE

Region: India

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India

India

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Dundas, Paul. *The Jains* (2nd ed.). London: Routledge, 2002.
- Source 2: Cort, John E. *Jains in the World: Religious Values and Ideology in India*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2001.
- Source 3: Cort, John E. (ed.). *Open Boundaries: Jain Communities and Cultures in Indian History*. Albany, NY: SUNY Press, 1998.

Notes: Jain Studies is a small but rapidly growing field of study within the broader field of South Asian religious studies.

Reference: Cort, John E.. *Jains in the World*. Oxford University Press, 2001.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=PZk-4HOMzsoC>.

Reference: Cort, John E.. *Open Boundaries*. SUNY Press, 1998.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Open_Boundaries.html?hl=&id=WWfnXbVWjKcC.

Reference: Dundas, Paul. *The Jains*. London: Routledge, n.d..
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Jains.html?hl=&id=jt6-YXE2aUwC.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://jainpedia.org/>
- Source 1 Description: Jainpedia is an online encyclopedia edited by Nalini Balbir (Sorbonne) with entries written by scholars and practitioners; it was created and supported by the Institute of Jainology, London
- Source 2 URL: <https://pluralism.org/jainism>
- Source 2 Description: Harvard University Pluralism Project's overview of Jainism
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.jaina.org/default.aspx>
- Source 3 Description: Website of the Federation of Jain Associations in North America (JAINA), the main

organization for Jains in the US and Canada that hosts biennial conventions and youth groups

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://jainelibrary.org/>

– Source 1 Description: The Jain e-Library is an online repository of mainly Svetambar Jain primary and secondary texts in Sanskrit, Prakrit, modern Indic vernaculars, and English. Texts range from canonical sources to contemporary scholarship in Indian languages and educational resources in English

– Source 2 URL: <https://jainworld.com/>

– Source 2 Description: A Digambar site that gives a comprehensive overview of Jain philosophy, practices, and texts in English translation

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.sacred-texts.com/jai/>

– Source 3 Description: English translations of four Svetambara Jain canonical texts by H. Jacobi in the Sacred Books of the East series

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Historically, Jains have competed for patronage from kings alongside other Indic religious communities. Mass conversions to Jainism happened in the medieval period on the strength of charismatic monks. Later bhakti traditions in the early modern period may have drawn some Jains to Krishna devotional traditions, such as the Pusti Marg, in western India. While few Jains openly proselytize, some Jain communities have effected changes in cultural practices among tribal communities in rural Rajasthan through philanthropic efforts (schools, hospitals).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

– No

Notes: Jains are generally full participants in social and political life in contemporary India. They were granted religious minority status in India in 2014.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

— Yes

Notes: Jains are considered generally considered part of the fabric of Indian society; there is a widespread acceptance of Jainism as one of several "dharma" traditions originating in India.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

— No

Notes: There have been several instances of Jain practices coming under public scrutiny (e.g. children performing fasting, child initiation, and efforts to get governments to ban meat sales during Jain holidays). The practice of fasting to death (sallekhana, santhara) was declared illegal as a form of suicide in 2015 by the Rajasthan High Court; the decision was later stayed by the Indian Supreme Court (suicide was decriminalized by an act of parliament in 2017, making the ruling moot).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

— Yes

Notes: Generally, Jains fit into everyday life of South Asia and relations between Jains and Hindus, or Jains and other religious communities is not openly hostile.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

— No

Notes: There are a few limited instances of open demonstrations against Jains, such as in the Mumbai suburb of Thane in 2015, when the Maharashtra Navnirman Sena (MNS), a sons-of-the-soil political organization and offshoot of the Shiv Sena, barbecued chicken in front of a Jain temple to protest a statewide ban on meat sales during the Jain holiday of Paryushan. Jains and Jain practices were characterized as non-Maharashtrian (non-Maratha).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

— Yes

Notes: Rare instances of violence between Jain sectarian communities have been recorded in news stories and scholarship. The "Bahubali Hill Affair" in 1984 showed the depth of divisions between Svetambar and Digambar Jains in Maharashtra as groups from both sects competed for control of a local pilgrimage site. More recently, Digambar Jains in Karnataka have expressed resentment over Svetambar Jains, mainly hailing from northern and western India, "reviving" and restoring abandoned temples in the state, calling it "encroachment."

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

— No

Notes: For the most part, sectarian conflicts have been over control of religious sites and have been fought in the Indian court system. Diaspora Jains in North America frequently pride themselves on their local community's success in accommodating all sects within their temples, leading recent scholarship to identify diaspora Jainism as both a non-sectarian or inter-sectarian form of the tradition: non-sectarian especially in terms of children's education, with an effort to find common denominators in points of doctrine and practice; inter-sectarian

in terms of bringing the images, symbols, practices and observances under the same roof in the space of the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: There have been limited examples of groups expressing open hostility toward Jains. The Anup Mandal is a self-proclaimed Marxist organization based in Rajasthan that blames Jains for control and manipulation of financial markets and blames Jain mendicants in particular for withholding monsoon rains. There are several instances of Jain monks and nuns being struck and killed in road accidents that Jains have accused the Anup Mandal of perpetrating, including the death of a prominent monk, Muni Jambuvijaya, and several members of his troupe in 2009. No prosecutions have yet resulted from these accidents.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

– No

Notes: Aside from limited examples of violence toward Jains, they are generally considered part of Indian society and live peacefully with their neighbors. While not all Jains are wealthy, the overall wealth of the Jain communities in India insulates them from violence.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Most Jains' sectarian affiliation comes through their caste identity, which generally tends to match up with specific mendicant lineages (gacchas) within each sect.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: There are several groups that have formed devotional communities around charismatic monks, nuns, or laymen. For example, the Kanji Swami Panth follows the teachings of the twentieth-century monk who converted from being a Svetambara monk to a Digambara layman. Additionally, Rakeshbhai Jhavery (b. 1966) has recently developed a devotional following based on his reading of the works of a late nineteenth-century Jain layman and religious seeker, Shrimad Rajacandra (1867-1901). Gyanmati Mataji (b. 1934) is a Digambar "aryika" (a laywoman who lives as a mendicant, as the Digambar tradition does not allow women to become mendicants formally) who has developed a devotional following in light of her "revival" of the Jain pilgrimage site at Hastinapur and several other places.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Caste communities frequently cover several socio-economic class levels, though Jains tend demographically to middle and upper classes in terms of wealth. Recent charismatic movements appeal to different classes and educational backgrounds.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Some people have "converted" to Jainism by adopting Jain practices. There are some examples of Hindus converting to Jainism by joining mendicant orders. There are few non-Indian converts to Jainism.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Jains generally support one of the two major political parties in India, the Indian National Congress (INC) and the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The general distinction is between "observant" and "non-observant" Jains.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 4500000

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.36

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Svetambara and Digambara canons differ greatly. Both sects agree that the original discourses of the last founder, Mahavira, were lost over time. The Svetambara canon (agamas) consists of 45 texts among image-worshipping (murtipujak), 32 among non-image-worshipping (Sthanakavasi, Terapanthi); it is considered the recollections of Mahavira's followers or works of learned early patriarchs, with acknowledged lacunae (e.g. the 12th text of the main part of the canon, the angas [limbs], is considered lost). The texts are composed mainly in Ardha-Magadhi with a few in Maharashtra, both Prakrit languages. The Digambara canon consists of a "six-part" (satkhanda) text of doctrine composed and commented on by early sectarian leaders, as well as the five major texts by Kundakunda (4th-8th c. CE), whose works cover doctrine, ontology, soteriology, and ethics.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Notes: All canonical scriptures in both major sects exist in written form. High ranking mendicants commit scriptures to memory.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: The Svetambara Jain scriptures are generally thought to be the recollections of the discourses of the last founder of the tradition, Mahavira. Although his exact words were lost within a few generations of his death, the canonical texts were accepted as the authentic recollections of Mahavira's disciples (ganadharas). The Digambara tradition also holds that Mahavira's original teachings were lost; their response was to

codify proper practice and doctrine and to enshrine those works as the "agamas." The later works of Kundakunda are considered as important as the six-part canon and are more widely read and respected among Digambar Jains today.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Several works of the Svetambara Jain canon are attributed to the authorship of certain early patriarchs of the tradition, especially Bhadrabahu (4th-3rd c. BCE). Several later works are attributed to other monks. The Digambara six-part text is based on the discourses of the first-century CE monk Dharasena. The scripture is considered to be parts of two texts also accepted in the Svetambara canon, though the Svetambaras considered the second of the two texts now lost (the Dristivada, which is based on Mahavira's original teachings, known as the Purvas or Original Discourses).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Jain temples share much in common with Hindu temple architecture, with some distinctive features. Most notably, in western India, Jain temples are frequently enclosed by a surrounding wall in which smaller shrines (devakulikas) are situated.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: There is usually one temple per neighborhood in cities and towns in India; in the US and other diaspora situations, there is generally one temple in each metropolitan area where Jains reside.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: The largest Jain temple in western India is the 15th-century temple to Rsabhanatha (Adinatha) at Ranakpur, Rajasthan. Major pilgrimage sites include Shatrunjay, a "temple city" atop the hill overlooking the town of Palitana, Gujarat; Girnar, a temple complex atop Girnar hill near Junagadh, Gujarat; and the Dilwara temples atop Mt. Abu in the Sirohi region of southern Rajasthan. The colossal statue of Bahubali located at Sravana Belagola, Karnataka is the most famous Digambar religious site.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 17

Notes: This is the height of the statue of Bahubali at Sravana Belagola, Karnataka

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Notes: Temples range in size and vary greatly throughout India. The largest temples are found at major pilgrimage sites, while more modest temples can be found in neighborhoods in cities throughout India.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Tombs:

– No

Notes: While there is evidence of a Jain stupa cult in early Mathura, they appear to have abandoned it by the first century CE. There is some evidence of interred relic worship in the contemporary Sthanakavasi tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: Jains follow the general South Asian custom of cremating their dead. However, there are a number of cenotaphs and memorials to deceased prominent mendicants. The cremation sites of particular Svetambara Kharatara Gaccha monks have also become sites of major shrines, such as in Mehrauli (Delhi), where the monk Jinacandrasuri II ("Manidhari," d. 1166) was cremated, and in Malpura, Rajasthan, where Jinakushalasuri (d. 1332) was cremated. These figures are regarded as deified monks who continue to intercede on Jains' behalf, known as the "Dada Guru Devs" (Grandfather Teacher Gods). These cremation sites (and other temples featuring these monks) are known as Dadabaris (Gardens of the Grandfathers).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Temples:

— Yes

Notes: Aside from the major sectarian division between Svetambara and Digambara Jains, Jains are also divided between those who worship images and those who do not. Image-worshipping Jains (murtipujak) are the majority in both sects. Two major sects of Svetambaras-- the Sthanakavasi and Terapanthi--reject image worship.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Altars:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Devotional markers:

— Yes

Notes: Mendicants wear all white, unstitched cloth in the Svetambara tradition; monks (muni, sadhu) wear no clothing at all in the Digambara tradition. Aryikas in the Digambar tradition are technically laywomen who live as nuns. Ordinary laymen and laywomen do not wear distinctive clothing that would mark them as Jain apart from Hindu, but when visiting the temple wear special "puja clothes" that are unhemmed and clean or not previously worn.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

— Yes

Notes: Major Svetambara pilgrimage sites include Shatrunjay (Palitana, Gujarat), Girnar (Junagadh, Guj.), Mt. Abu (Sirohi, Rajasthan), Sammet Shikhar (Jharkhand). Other prominent temples include the Adinatha temple at Ranakpur (Rajasthan) and the Parshvanath temple at Shankheshvar (Gujarat), among many others. Prominent Digambara pilgrimage sites include the colossus of Bahubali at Gommateshvara Hill at Sravana Belagola, Karnataka, and the Mahavirji temple in Hindaun, Rajasthan. Other prominent sites include the Mudbidri monastery (matha) in Karnataka and Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

- Yes [specify]: Colossal statues of Bahubali are prominent in Karnataka and at several other Digambar sites (e.g. Gwalior)

Notes: Recently, a 34-foot statue of Śrīmad Rājacandra was erected by the Shrimad Rajchandra Mission at their main ashram in Dharampur, Gujarat.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is iconography present:

- Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

- At home
- Only religious public space

Notes: Images of the Jinas (aka Tirthankaras) come in two basic forms: standing with arms at rest by their sides in a position called "abandoning the body" (kayotsarga), or seated in lotus position (padmasana) with hands overlapping in a position of meditation (dhyana mudra). In addition to the Jinas, Jains also worship images of protector gods and goddesses (shasan devata), as well as those of the goddesses Lakshmi and Sarasvati. Jains also venerate images of important monks, especially two of Mahavira's disciples, Gautama Swami and Sudharman Swami. One Svetambara sect, the Kharatara Gaccha, worships images of four medieval monks, the Dada Guru Devs ("Grandfather Guru Gods"), who are considered deities. Deities are considered lay Jains who can intercede on behalf of Jains for worldly wellbeing.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

- Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

- Yes

Notes: In the Svetambara murtipujak tradition, enamel eyes are often fixed onto the statues of Jinas and other deities; images of deceased monks and nuns often have eyes affixed on them as well. The Digambara tradition does not affix eyes on their images.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

- Yes

Notes: There are two prominent Jain deities with zoomorphic features. One is

Manibhadra Vīr, a protector deity (śāsan devatā) often depicted with a human body and bull's head. The other is Pārśva Yakṣa, another guardian deity with a human body and elephant's head. Jains, like Buddhists, have been closely linked with yakṣas and yakṣīs, "nature spirits," since their earliest iconographic depictions. Each of the 24 Jinas has a male and female pair of deities. The most famous of these pairs are the god Dharanendra and goddess Padmāvātī, tutelary deities of the 23rd Jina, Pārśvanātha. They are depicted as cobras or as humans with cobra lower halves. Images of Pārśvanātha are distinctive for having a seven-headed cobra appearing over his head, recalling how Dharanendra returned Pārśva's kindness in a previous existence by saving cobras from being sacrificed. Here, Dharanendra shelters the meditating Jina in his moment of achieving omniscience (kevala jñāna), the precondition to liberation (mokṣa). Padmāvātī is also depicted in fully anthropomorphic form; her own vehicle is a cobra-headed rooster.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

— Yes

Notes: Kṣetrapāls (land protector deities) are prominently worshipped in western India. Manibhadra Vīr whose most prominent temple is in Ujjain, MP is also often depicted as a rocky outcropping with minimal iconography. Other kṣetrapāls are similarly depicted as rocky outcroppings at temple sites, often smeared with vermilion paste and frequently bearing enamel eyes.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

— Yes

Notes: Jinas, other liberated beings, prominent deceased monks and nuns, and a wide range of guardian deities are depicted in anthropomorphic form in sculpture and painting. Some images are worshipped, while others are memorials (particularly those of deceased monks and nuns)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

— Yes

Notes: Jinas and other liberated beings are often depicted with a pair of footprints (pādukā, caraṇa) to depict their absence from the transmigratory world. One particular image used in the Digambar tradition, called the siddha, depicts the absent liberated soul in the form of an outline of the standing Jina, usually cut out of a flat piece of metal situated on a stand.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

— Yes

Notes: Jain images of the cosmos are common in painting. They depict the universe in

the shape of a man with legs spread and arms akimbo. The plane of humans, animals, and plants is located at the waist; the 14 heavens are located in the diamond shaped area of the torso while the seven hells occupy the trapezoidal area of the legs. The torments of the hells are often depicted in gruesome detail. Additionally, the siddhaśīla, the crescent-shaped abode of liberated souls, is situated at the top of the universe. Jains often depict the siddhaśīla under the Jina in paintings and Jains make a crescent shape out of rice when performing dravya pūjā (worship with items) with a small cluster of rice above it to depict the location of the liberated soul that each Jain aspires to attain.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

— Yes

Notes: Jains consider the swastika a key Jain symbol and interpret it as a depiction of the four categories of rebirth: human, divine, hell-being, and plant/animal. They often place four dots in the four hollows created by the arms of the swastika to depict these possible rebirths. In its fullest expression, Jains place three dots to symbolize the "three jewels" of the tradition, namely Right View, Right Knowledge, and Right Conduct. Above that, they place a crescent shape horizontally with the ends pointing upward to depict the abode of liberated souls (śiddhaśīla) with a dot above it to depict the final destination of liberated souls. The symbol adopted widely by Jains to represent their tradition includes the outline of the Jain conception of the universe, an hourglass-like shape with a trapezoidal base and an elongated hexagon atop. Within, Jains place the swastika with three dots and dotted crescent. Below this, they place a hand, palm forward with fingers straight, pointing upward. This is the iconographic hand pose indicating "fear not" (abhaya mudra). Within the hand is written "Ahimsa" (non-harm) within an eight-spoked wheel, which depicts the five worship-worthy figures (Jinas, liberated beings, and the three levels of the monastic hierarchy) as well as the three jewels. The hand symbol is also used independently as a symbol of the tradition. Jains also frequently display the "eight auspicious items" (aṣṭa maṅgala), which differs completely between the Śvetāmbara and Digambara sects.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Humans:

— Yes

Notes: The Jinas are considered humans who attained spiritual liberation and taught the path for others to follow. They are depicted in sculpture and painting and are the central objects of veneration at a Jain temple. In addition, important monks, including two of Mahavira's disciples, Gautama and Sudharman, are often found in temples. Further, images of deified monks receive worship in the Śvetāmbara Kharatara Gaccha, known as the Dada Guru Devs. Additionally, prominent monks and nuns often have statues or relief carving depictions as memorials. Recently, images of the 19th-century layman and religious savant Śrīmad Rājacandra (1867-1901) have been made and worshipped by the Shrimad Rajchandra Mission of Dharampur, Gujarat. Beyond these, photographs of deceased loved ones are often placed in Jain resthouses (dharmśālās) and dining halls (bhojanśālas) at important temples and pilgrimage sites by donor patrons, and feature in the frontispieces of many books and other publications.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

In a human form:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

In form of an inanimate object(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Yes [specify]: As heavenly being (a deity) or as a hell-being

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ **Cremation:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ **Mummification:**
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ **Interment:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ **Cannibalism:**
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ **Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):**
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ **Feeding to animals:**
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ **Secondary burial:**
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ **Re-treatment of corpse:**
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
– Yes [specify]: They know locations of hidden treasures and places inaccessible to humans.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits can reward:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits can punish:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Signs can come from animals, plants, natural phenomena, etc.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Karmically, deities are "offices" occupied by souls for discrete periods of time.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Food:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Incest:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Other sexual practices:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: The only way karma is known and understood is through the teachings of the Jinas, who were omniscient at the time of their teaching.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Moral norms apply to:

- All individuals within society
- All individuals within contemporary world
- All individuals (any time period)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Jain mendicants take vows of celibacy (brahmacarya); some Jain laypersons take similar vows and live quasi-monastic lifestyles. For most Jains, however, marriage is considered the appropriate outlet for sexual activity.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Some Jain couples take vows of celibacy after they have all the children they plan to have. Jains generally adhere to the idea of quelling the passions, including sexual desire.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Fasting is not required; however, it is an extremely common practice among Jains (it is considered the primary form of tapas, asceticism) and Jain laywomen especially perform fasts regularly, as they are considered the center of the religious wellbeing of their families.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Observant Jains follow a strict vegetarian diet that includes prohibitions on root vegetables (which are followed intermittently by laypeople), honey, figs, and certain other foods that are considered violent to harvest or eat.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: Jain mendicants apparently used to perform austerities (tapas) that included painful postures or remaining in positions that became painful over time in order to shed karma accrued to the soul (ātman, jīva). However, the later tradition appears to have moved away from these kinds of practices in favor of more community-observed fasts and other austerities.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: The practice of choosing to die by starvation, called sallekhana or santhara, is a controversial act that Jains have defended from charges that it is tantamount to suicide. Jain apologists argue that that suicide is an act of passion, while the slow, patient performance of sallekhana can only be completed with control over the senses. In 2015, the Rajasthan High Court sided with human rights groups that sought to have it characterized as suicide owing to issues of coercion, arguing that social pressure explains why elderly widows are the most numerous demographic of sallekhana performances. The decision was stayed by the Indian Supreme Court that same year; suicide was decriminalized by an act of parliament in 2017, making the decision moot.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Jains are expected to give a portion of their wealth to support the local temple and religious community's activities. This is done through public spectacles, such as the auctioning of the right to perform certain rituals or to host ritual objects in one's home at festival times. Other forms of patronage of institutions and mendicants are fields of merit making (puṇya) that reflect back on the donor in the form of "good karma" and social accolades. However, while wealthier members of a community face pressure to contribute appropriately to the community's needs, Jain laymen are expected to stay within their means and not overspend on religious observances; it is considered unseemly to overspend, especially if it might harm a family's welfare for the subsequent year.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Mendicant lifestyles are highly regimented with daily observances and practices. They are required to wander from place to place during eight months of the year. They are required to stay in one place during the four-month rainy season (caturmāsa, comāsu). Lay Jains are not required to attend rituals at the temple, but frequently do, with the greatest time commitment coming during the eight-day period of Paryushan (Śvetāmbara) or ten-day period of Daśalakṣaṇa (Digambara), during which lay Jains will eat bland, simple food, dress in simple clothing and perform the ritualized confession (pratikramaṇa) daily. Daily observances of ritual worship of images at the temple often include a 48-minute period of meditation in a standing posture (kāyotsarga).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Jain mendicants and laity frequently perform aggressive fasting. Some forms of fasting include the year-long period of eating just every other day. One of the most common fasts is the oli, in which Jains eat only bland food for a week. One of the most commonly performed lengthy fasts is a month of no food or a week without food or water. In 2016, 13-year-old Aradhana Samdhariya of Hyderabad died after completing a 68-day fast. Laywomen and girls perform fasts more than any other sector of Jain society because women are considered the center of family piety and pious girls bring prestige to their families. Aradhana's funeral was attended by over 600 people, her funeral procession was labeled a "celebration" (śobha yātrā) and attendees hailed her as a "child ascetic" (bāl tapasvī).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: While the degree of adherence to Jain principles is up to each individual in the community, vegetarianism has become the sine qua non of Jain identity in recent times. Records exist going back to the sixteenth century of Jains urging Mughal emperor Akbar to issue a ban on meat sales during Paryushan. Jains generally seek to quell passions through abstemious behavior meant to cultivate self control. Recent efforts to turn ascetic practices into societal ethics have met with limited success, but is most prominently seen in Acharya Tulsi's (1914-1997) "Anuvrat Movement" (Lesser Vows), an attempt by the leader of the Śvetāmbara Terāpanth to reform society by making social goods of the ascetic vows for laypeople, which all but the most pious lay Jains themselves ever formally took.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 24

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100000

Notes: Festivals at local temples involve members of a neighborhood (a few hundred to a few thousand at most); larger pilgrimages can involve thousands of people. The largest festival happens once every 12 years, the mahāmastakābhiṣeka (great showering) of the image of Bāhubali at Sravana Belagola in Karnataka, which was attended by “hundreds of thousands” during its last celebration in 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 168

Notes: Temple rituals happen on a daily basis in India, though weekly performances are most common by families at their local temples. Festivals happen several times throughout the year, such as Mahavira’s birthday (Jayanti) in March-April, and his attainment of liberation (mokṣa) on Dīvālī (October-November). Pilgrimages happen annually to different sites, though families may

go on such pilgrimages just once in a lifetime to each. The longest interval for the performance of any ritual is 12 years, the showering of the image of Bāhubali at Sravana Belagola in Karnataka.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

— No

Notes: There is an increasing prominence given to texts in the regulation of Jain orthodoxy, which has come through increased access to sacred texts available in translation and owing to an increased interest in learning the Prakrit languages in which they were composed.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

— Yes

Notes: Ritual manuals are published annually, with descriptions written by certain prominent mendicants. Most ritual performances are taught to children by their mothers or other family members, most often by female family members. Orthopraxy is more often regulated by members of the community than by elites such as mendicants.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

— Yes

Notes: While temple rituals are performed individually and observances often done at home, there is a strong inclination to individualized praxis. However, the annual festival of Paryushan and other annual festivals, as well as annual pilgrimages and even rituals that happen every 12 years (such as the abhiṣek of Bāhubali at Sravana Belagola) entail large group assemblies that involve units from a neighborhood to entire caste communities to even larger assemblies of people.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

— No

Notes: Observant Jains are teetotalers and general abstemiousness is enjoined as a moral and ethical good. There is no use of intoxicants in Jain religious rituals or other practices.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Notes: Fellow Jains are called "sādharmikas" ("co-religionists"). Gujaratis and others address each other as "brother" (bhai) or "sister" (bahen), elders are addressed as grandparents or as aunts or uncles, but there are no religious requirements or injunctions to do so.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Jains have their own caste groupings (jātis) within the larger Indian society. These are largely endogamous groups with common geographical origins or a common occupational role. Jains have largely hailed from mercantile caste communities in western India since the medieval period. While some mendicant orders (gacchas) or sects have clear affiliations with particular caste communities, castes and sects may or may not overlap. For example, all Śvetāmbara Terāpanthis are from the Agarwal caste, yet not all Agarwals are Terāpanthis (or even Jains). Similarly, all Kharatara Gaccha Jains are from either the Śrīmal or Oswal castes, yet the Kharatara Gaccha's sub-lineages are divided along caste lines.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: Prominent Jain laymen have famously provided famine relief going back to the medieval period. Jain magnates donated grain from their stores to keep people on their land and sold grain at cost to the British army during the colonial period. However, these individual acts of philanthropic charity could not be called "institutional," nor are there in place now Jain organizations whose primary mission is to prevent or help out during famines.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Jain farmers in southern Maharashtra receive government and other charitable benefits during times of need, some of which come from charities organized and run by wealthier Jains.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Some Jain organizations provide poverty relief and serve disadvantaged communities (tribal, low caste, etc.). The Śvetāmbar Terāpanth works in poor, rural areas of southern Rajasthan, building and running schools and charity hospitals. The Veerayatan Organization is a global charity that runs schools for poor children. The Shrimad Rajchandra Mission of Dharampur, Gujarat has opened a number of schools and hospitals and maintains a constant online fundraising campaign to fund its charitable operations. However, none of these organizations are considered mainstream and the latter two are considered controversial in the wider Jain community.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Few Jains are in need of poverty relief. However, the most prominent group of Jains of lesser economic class are farmers in southern Maharashtra, who benefit from government programs, Jain charities, and other charities.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: For the infirm, mainly. Elder care is still largely the purview of families, with support from the broader community when needed. The Bhagwan Mahaveer Viklang Sahayata Samiti produces and fits patients with the "Jaipur Foot," a low-cost or free prosthetic leg for people in need.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Jains not only educate their own adherents, but run numerous schools and charity schools.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Jains have one of the highest literacy rates of any religious community in South Asia for both men and women. Young Jain men and women frequently have college and graduate degrees.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There are caste pancayats (councils) as well as mendicant leaders associated with specific caste communities. The level of influence these bureaucracies have depends on several factors, including location (urban/rural), caste, and place of origin.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Jains participate at all levels in the Indian government and in the governments of other countries where they reside.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: Jain merchants were famous for storing grain in the medieval, early modern and colonial eras, distributing it to their locales during times of famine.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: As Jains are generally well off, I am not sure if they require such services.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Auctions of the rights to perform rituals or to host ritual objects in the home during festival times are a major fundraiser for most local temples. There is substantial social pressure to spend in proportion to one's means in these situations. However, there is no formal tax or tithe levied on community members to support their institutions. There are numerous opportunities for patronage of temple objects and temple maintenance is often done through donations in India. In diaspora communities and in several places in India, temple construction and maintenance is done by subscription.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Jains frequently boast that they pay more in income tax than any other religious community in India.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Jains interact with the local police forces in India and in the other countries where they live.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: There are caste-based pañcayats that can adjudicate matters of observance and propriety, with enforcement backed by social pressure and opprobrium rather than by legal force. Not all Jain communities have operational pañcayats and the relative power each exerts is dependent on geography, caste, and location (urban/rural).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Those of the states in the countries in which they reside.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: In very rare cases.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: Among Jain caste communities that deal in the gem industry, bad or improper business dealings can lead to relocating the offender to less important positions or those with less responsibility.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: These could take the form of fines in some cases.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: None other than the state apparatus in the countries in which Jains reside.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Jains tend to follow Hindu civil law in India, though there are indications that Jains allowed women to inherit property prior to the colonial period when civil law was standardized into either Hindu or Muslim law codes.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Only those of the states of the countries in which they reside.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: While generally discouraged within the community as a violent occupation, there are some Jains who serve in the Indian armed forces. Historically, prominent Jains have served as ministers and generals to Hindu kings.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Anyone can access the Prakrit texts of the Jain canons now that they are available in printed editions. However, prior to the printing press, few Jains, even mendicants, formally studied the Jain canon in the original languages and instead engaged with their ideas through vernacular commentaries or through the teachings and counsel of mendicants. The largest barrier to access to the canonical texts is currently knowledge of the Prakrit languages in which they are written (Ardha-Māgadhī and Māhārāṣṭrī for Śvetāmbaras; Śauraseni for Digambaras), although Indic vernacular and even English translations now exist for many of these texts. Several hymns and philosophical works exist in Sanskrit and vernaculars. Gujarati is becoming a de facto lingua sacra among Śvetāmbar Jains in India and the diaspora due to the sheer volume of devotional and instructional literature available in that language, outstripping Hindi, which is more commonly spoken by North Indian and diaspora Jains.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: While Sanskrit and some Prakrits are common South Asian literary languages, they are not necessarily or exclusively offered through institutions outside the Jain community.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Jains have composed works in Sanskrit, Prakrits, and vernaculars that are not the exclusive purview of the tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Jain calendar is also called a pañcāṅga and includes many major and minor holidays.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Notes: While there are some Jain farmers, particularly in southern Maharashtra, they provide food to the general market and not just to other Jains.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Jains generally purchase food on the open market in India and elsewhere, despite their dietary restrictions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 900 BCE - 2020 CE

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